

Multifactor Leadership Styles and School-Based Management for Quality Education in the Basic Level

Cantos, Rina A.

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The study sought to determine the relationship of the multifactor leadership styles of school heads with that of school-based management in Sariaya West District, Schools Division of Quezon for school year 2022-2023.

The study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational design where a researcher-made survey questionnaire was employed in gathering the data needed. The data were statistically analyzed using mathematical average and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The respondents of the study were composed of 152 teachers from six (6) big schools in the District.

Transformational leadership is moderately correlated with school-based management at 0.01 level. According to the survey, the majority of school heads used a transactional leadership style with an average mean of 4.01. The accountability and ongoing development of school-based management show the power of the school leaders. According to Muturi (2021), in laissez-faire leadership, the head teacher believes that there should be no rules and regulations since everyone has a sense of responsibility. As a result, a laissez-faire school's environment may be more creative and fulfilling for those involved in the school management system. The results of the study helped generate the following conclusion: At the 0.01 significant level, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between school leaders' multifactor leadership styles and the level of school-based management is statistically not supported. The findings of this study may enhance leadership and school governance curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources., School heads may implement a variety of leadership philosophies and assessment tools. Teachers may participate in decision-making processes, particularly those involving school-based management and its procedures. The current study may serve as the foundation for future research on management practices in schools on leadership styles of school heads.

KEYWORDS: Multifactor Leadership Styles, School-based Management, Transformational, Transactional, and Laissez-faire Styles

INTRODUCTION

Educational leaders play a vital role in the success of the school. They are the cornerstone on which learning communities' function and grow. A rapidly changing work environment requires administrators to demonstrate traits and attitudes that will make them effective leaders in their school organization. Education plays an important role in equipping an individual with the necessary knowledge and skills to become productive members of society. For this matter, effective school administrators are expected to be academically goal oriented and supervise instructional and co-curricular practices accordingly.

A leadership style is a leader's method of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. Leaders and their leadership skills also play an important role in the growth of any organization. Leadership refers to the process of influencing the behavior of people in a manner that they strive willingly and enthusiastically towards the achievement of group objectives. A leader should have the ability to maintain good interpersonal relations with the followers or subordinates and motivate them to help in achieving the organizational objectives.

Leadership is one of the keys in achieving school goals and objectives. As cited by Rapatan (2014), good leaders never give their leadership away. However, leaders do share both the rewards and responsibility in leading. Responsibility without authority disables rather than empowers followers. There should be a balance between delegated authority and responsibility. Good leaders should know the principle of delegation. Learning effective delegation creates harmonious relationship in an institution or organization especially in the school. Good leaders should set SMART (specific, measurable, attainable, reliable, and time-bounded) goals, clear expectations, and distinguish between execution and formulation.

In leadership, school heads should know how to drive the team because it is superior to individual effort. Team involves more people, thus affording more resources, ideas, and energy than would an individual. It maximizes a leader's potential and minimizes weaknesses. Strength and weaknesses are more exposed in individuals. In the modern perspective, leadership can be

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transformational or transactional. Transformational leadership empowers followers by allowing them to accept challenges, such as taking on and “owning” a new project. This means that leaders do not ask more of followers when they know the followers can accomplish. Followers might still feel a sense of risk in accepting what they see as a challenge. However, a transformational leader does what is necessary to ensure that real risk is low. The leader makes certain that empowered followers have the resources, skills, and knowledge they need to succeed, (Taylor and Rowan, 2012).

On the other hand, transactional leadership is proactive. It works to change the organizational culture by implementing new ideas. Employees achieve objectives through higher ideals and moral values. Similarly, it motivates followers by encouraging them to put group interests first. Each behavior is directed towards each individual to express consideration and support. It promotes creative and innovative ideas to solve problems (Odumeru and Ifeanyi, 2013).

In this study, Multifactor leadership style is assessed through the use of Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ—also known as MLQ 5X short or the standard MLQ). MLQ measures a broad range of leadership types from passive leaders, to leaders who give contingent rewards to followers, to leaders who transform their followers into becoming leaders themselves. The MLQ identifies the characteristics of a transformational leader and helps individuals discover how they measure up in their own eyes and in the eyes of those with whom they work. Success can be measured through a retesting program to track changes in leadership style.

Full-Range Leadership Model

The Full-Range Leadership Model (FRLM) evolved directly from the work of James MacGregor Burns. In 1978, Burns argued that leadership was either transactional or transformational. Transactional leaders lead through social exchanges, transformational leaders develop their followers and motivate and /or inspire them to achieve extraordinary levels of success. This last offering was critical as it explained those situation in which followers exceeded all expectations—even their own- to achieve success

The results of the study may provide insights and informational benefits to the following:

Officials of the Schools Division. This study may help them design new seminars and trainings on leadership skills as well as transforming the educational community to increase achievements and for further improvement of the curriculum.

School Heads. This study may be on a new facet of leadership to help them improve practices that create changes in their leadership and face difficulties of the reforms in education program.

Teachers. This study may help them to be more aware of the type of leadership of the school heads particularly in pursuing their career in educational management;

Students. This study may help them to know the leadership style of school administrators in the implementation of K to 12 programs now and in the future.

Future Researchers. This study may provide them ideas and insights that may be helpful in their research endeavor.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To determine the relationship of the multifactor leadership styles of school heads with that of school-based management in Sariaya West District, Schools Division of Quezon for school year 2022-2023.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive-correlational research design was used in this quantitative investigation. This design aims to describe the relationship among variables rather than to infer cause and effect relationship. Descriptive correlational studies are useful for describing how one phenomenon is related to another situations where the researcher has no control over the independent variables, the variables that are believed to cause or influence the dependent or outcome variable.

The researcher used descriptive design to determine the relationship of multifactor leadership styles with that of school-based management for quality education in the basic level.

Respondents were described in terms of age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, plantilla position and years in service (Appendix H). The respondents of the study were the teachers in six (6) targeted elementary schools in Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon. The total of 194 teachers were gathered from the District Office of which 152 samples were randomly chosen. The study utilized a survey questionnaire to gather data needed in answering the research problem. The instrument consisted of two parts: Part I: Multifactor Leadership Styles, Part II: School-Based Management Components

A random sampling technique was utilized in the study. The researcher targeted a total of 152 classroom teachers in the six big schools of Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon.

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher submitted a letter requesting that the study be done in the Sariaya West District, Schools Division of Quezon.

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A two-section questionnaire was adopted by the researcher from reliable sources. The questionnaire's content was evaluated for validity and reliability. Suggestions of the evaluators were incorporated into the research questionnaire.

The gathered data in this study were treated statistically using varied statistical tools.

To determine the level of respondents' perception of the components of multifactor leadership styles of school heads, average mean and standard deviation were employed.

To determine the extent of respondents' perception on school-based management, mean and standard deviation were also employed.

To test the significant relationship between multifactor leadership style and school-based management as variables of the study, Pearsons' Product -Moment Correlation Coefficient was used at 0.01 level of probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This presents the data gathered on multifactor leadership styles of school heads and the extent of perception on school-based management of school leaders.

Transformational Leadership Style of School Heads

Transformational leadership style is defined as a leadership style in which leaders encourage, inspire and motivate employees to innovate and create change that will help grow and shape the future success of the company.

On the succeeding table provides the perception of the respondents on the transformational leadership style of the school leader.

The transformational leader needs transformational leadership to manage the change in an organization. The transformational leader acts as a role model for the followers, enabling them to recognize the corporate vision, (KEMI, 2014). Furthermore, by copying the leader's behavior and internalizing it, the followers tend to respect and trust the leader (Bass, 2008).

Table 1. Summary Table on the Perceived Level of Transformational Leadership Style of School Heads

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Idealized Influence	3.97	0.81	Fairly Often
2. Inspirational Motivation	3.98	0.76	Fairly Often
3. Intellectual Stimulation	3.40	0.74	Fairly Often
4. Individualized consideration	3.98	0.80	Fairly Often
Overall	3.83	0.78	Fairly Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00- Frequently (F), 3.50-4.49- Fairly Often (FO), 2.50-3.49- Sometimes (S), 1.50- 2.49- Once in a whole (OW), 1.00-1.49- Not at All (NA)

Table 1 demonstrates the summary that school leaders' perceived levels of transformational leadership were Inspiring motivation, with a mean of 3.98. This suggests that leaders that employ a transformational style of leadership tended to exhibit good behavior in their staff members, serve as role models for others in the building, and motivate staff members to up their game in order to reach academic requirements. And the head of the school has time to meet with the instructors, encourage them, and offer assistance in enhancing both their personal and professional lives inside the institution.

The ability to lead is a bond that encourages collaboration among instructors. The head of the school oversees and spreads innovation and change while staying in constant contact with the faculty (Ukaidi, 2016). Modern leaders, according to Raza et al. (2010), embrace a mindset that encourages creative thinking, broadens communication, cultivates optimism, supports employees, and creates a vision. The goal of all these characteristics is a transformational leadership style.

Transactional Leadership Style of School Heads

The most prevalent type of leadership found in many firms is described as transactional. This approach, sometimes known as "carrots and sticks," focuses on supervision, structure, and performance as well as instilling conformity inside the business.

Table 2. Summary Table on the Perception of Respondents on the Transactional Leadership Style of School Heads

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Contingent Reward	3.98	0.80	Fairly Often
2. Management-by-Exception	4.04	0.75	Fairly Often
Overall	4.01	0.775	Fairly Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00- Frequently (F), 3.50-4.49- Fairly Often (FO), 2.50-3.49- Sometimes (S), 1.50-2.49- Once in a whole (OW), 1.00-1.49- Not at All (NA)

Table 2 shows that management-by-exception, a transactional leadership style, is widely used by school leaders. Consequently, the average mean of 4.04 indicates that school leaders are resolving frequent problems in day-to-day operations and personnel management. Management-by-exception assesses whether you tell others the job requirements are content with the standard performance and are a believer in "if it ain't broke, don't fix it." School heads and teachers work together to set, communicate, and achieve specific measurable goals for the organization.

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Teachers who are qualified, inspired, and empowered are crucial in equipping youth and adults in each nation with the information, skills, and morals they need to live wholesome and satisfying lives (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2018). Teachers are one of the key factors of educational quality and learning outcomes since they have an influence on students' educational growth. So that they can have a beneficial influence on students' learning, instructors should perform to the best of their ability throughout educational activities (Bourn et al., 2017). Yet, instructors' productivity is correlated with their degree of motivation, which impacts not only their attitudes and views toward their profession but also the results and motivation of pupils.

Laissez-faire Leadership Style of School Heads

This kind of leadership allow their followers to have the autonomy to make their own decisions and manage their own tasks.

Table 3. Perceived Laissez-faire Leadership Style of School Heads

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. motivates others to strive more	4.11	.794	Fairly Often
2. allows others to do what they want	3.91	.817	Fairly Often
3. is contented of other's support which is absolutely essential	3.98	.849	Fairly Often
Overall	4.00	0.82	Fairly Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00- Frequently (F), 3.50-4.49- Fairly Often (FO), 2.50-3.49- Sometimes (S), 1.50-2.49- Once in a whole (OW)
1.00-1.49- Not at All (NA)

Table 3 demonstrates how school leaders encourage people to work harder, with a mean of 4.11 and a Likert scale interpretation of fairly often. In order to achieve the best levels of instruction for the students, school administrators must push instructors to their limits. On the other side, the mean score of 3.98 indicated that school administrators are happy with the technical support provided to the teachers and that technical support is thought to be crucial for helping instructors improve their methods of instruction.

Also, the mean score of 3.91 reveals that school leaders give people the to act any way they pleased as long as it advances the institution, particularly in the areas of teaching and learning and school administration.

Lack of clearly defined decision-making processes and minimal participation by the leader are characteristics of laissez-faire leadership. Because there is no defined limit on discussion time, decision-making and school administration are not very effective. The power of this style of leadership, however, is in the absence of hostility and conflicts within the school community.

According to Muturi (2021), in laissez-faire leadership, the head teacher believes that there should be no rules and regulations since everyone has a sense of responsibility. As a result, a laissez-faire school's environment may be more creative and fulfilling for those involved in the school management system. The average mean score of 4.00 demonstrated that school administrators typically use laissez faire leadership to oversee daily operations. The degree to which a head teacher is successful in achieving the school's goals, purpose, vision, and philosophy relies on how well she or he applies the right management techniques to the unique setting of the school.

Table 4. Summary Table on the Perceived Leadership Styles of School Heads

Leadership Styles	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Transformational	3.83	0.78	Fairly Often
2. Transactional	4.01	0.76	Fairly Often
3. Laissez -faire	4.00	0.82	Fairly Often
Overall	3.94	0.79	Fairly Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00- Frequently (F), 3.50-4.49- Fairly Often (FO), 2.50-3.49- Sometimes (S) 1.50-2.49- Once in a whole (OW)
1.00-1.49- Not at All (NA)

With a mean of 4.01, Table 4 demonstrate that the majority of school leaders employ a transactional leadership style. With a mean of 4.00, some of them engage in laissez-faire behavior. The school heads in the division have varied leadership styles, particularly in the implementation of school-based management, as evidenced by the fact that other school leaders exercise transformational leadership with a mean of 3.83 and interpreted as fairly often. Thus, the average mean of 3.94 denotes that these leadership styles are being practiced by the school heads fairly often.

Leadership is a bond that makes teachers work together in which the head of school manages and disseminates innovation and change, always in direct contact with teachers (Ukaidi, 2016). According to Raza et al (2010), modern leaders adopt an attitude that supports employees, prepare vision, cultivate hope, encourage creative thinking and broaden communication. All these features are directed towards a transformational leadership style.

School-Based Management of School Leaders

School-based management is best explained by as a strategy to improve education by transferring significant decision-making authority from state and district offices to individual schools.

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Table 5 shows that the strength of the school leaders is manifested in the accountability and continuous improvement with the mean of 3.42, standard deviation of 0.59 and interpreted as to a high extent of practice. This means that the school leaders practice the continuous improvement of the school in improving the governance and teaching practices with the end view of improving learning outcomes. A clear, transparent, inclusive and responsive accountability system is in place. This shows that the targeted schools collaboratively developed by community stakeholders, which monitors expected and actual performance. Roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective bodies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.

Table 5. Summary Table on the Extent of Practice of School-based Management of School Leaders

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Leadership and Governance	3.38	.60	High Extent of Practice
2. Curriculum and Instruction	3.36	.58	High Extent of Practice
3.Accountability and Continuous Improvement.	3.42	.58	High Extent of Practice
4. Management of Resources	3.38	.59	High Extent of Practice
Overall	3.39	0.59	High Extent of Practice

Legend: 3.50-4.00- Very High Extent of Practice, 2.50-3.49- High Extent of Practice, 1.50-2.49- Moderately Extent of Practice, 1.00-1.49- No Extent of Practice

Thus, the average mean of 3.39 denoted that the SBM had been thoroughly practiced by the school heads in the schools Division of Quezon. It shows that school head put students' needs first in order to provide them with high-quality instruction. The Department of Education developed a good technique which is school-based management. It is a simple approach to delegate major decision-making power from the state to the district and the specific school. For the learners, SBM creates a learning environment.

Test of Relationship between Variables

Multifactor Leadership Styles are correlated to school-based management system.

Table 6 demonstrates the moderate correlation between the leadership style of the school leaders and the degree of school-based management implementation. The more effectively school-based management is implemented, the stronger the head of school's leadership.

Transformational leadership style in terms of idealized influence behavior (r value= .618), inspirational motivation (r value= .660), intellectual stimulation (r value= .702), and individualized consideration (r value=.672) show a significant correlation to the components of school-based management in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and management and resources at 0.01 level of probability. Transactional leadership style as to contingent reward (r value=.588), and management-by-exception (r value=.611), indicate a significant correlation to the components of school-based management at 0.01 level of confidence. Laissez-faire leadership style (r value=.604) shows a significant correlation to school-based management of school leaders.

Table 6. Correlation Between Multifactor Leadership Styles and School-based Management of Practice.

	School-Based Management			
	A	B	C	D
Multifactor Leadership Styles				
• Transformational leadership				
Idealized influence	.618**	.530**	.525**	.515**
inspirational motivation;	.660**	.612**	.611**	.569**
intellectual stimulation; and	.702**	.633**	.647**	.616**
individualized consideration	.672**	.591**	.627**	.590**
• Transactional Leadership				
Contingent reward;	.636**	.576**	.586**	.554**
Active management-by-exception	.656**	.586**	.608**	.596**
• Laissez Faire Leadership	.680**	.585**	.582**	.569**

A. Leadership and Governance, B. Curriculum and Learning, C. Accountability and Continuous Improvement, D. Management and Resources

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As to curriculum and learning and accountability and continuous improvement, it revealed that the transformational leadership style is the best leadership style to practice in curriculum and learning. The study also revealed that employees wanted a kind of leader who serves as a role model for high ethical behavior instills pride, and gains respect, and trust. A leader who articulates a vision that is appealing and inspiring to the followers, a leader with inspirational motivation, challenge followers with high standards,

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communicate about future goals and provides meaning for the task at hand. A leader solicits follower idea and encourages their creativity.

The study revealed that the leadership style of school head practice in leadership and governance is laissez-faire leadership style. Wherein school heads have trust and reliance on their employees. It shows that employees wanted the kind of leader who let them develop their creativity, resources, and experiences to meet their goal, a leader who is confident in employees' abilities, a leader that gives guidance and takes responsibility when needed, and a leader who let their subordinates and team members have the real lead.

As the result revealed a moderate correlation between the leadership style of the school leaders and the degree of school-based management implementation, it indicates that school leaders can apply different leadership style in managing the components of school-based management for quality education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship of the multifactor leadership styles of school heads with that of the school-based management is statistically not sustained at 0.01 level of confidence.

In light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are given:

1. The Schools Division may entrust the school administrators to hold more training sessions and seminars on Multifactor leadership styles and practices and how they may relate to educational setting.
2. To enhance leadership and school governance, school directors may implement a variety of leadership philosophies and assessment tools. By sharing their ideas and experiences for raising the performance of the schools and students, school administrators can urge teachers and other stakeholders to get involved in the leadership of the school.
3. Teachers may participate in decision-making processes, particularly those who are involved in school-based management and its procedures.
4. The findings of this study may serve as the foundation for future researchers on management practices and leadership styles of school heads.

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